

Assessing Hypoxemia in Patients of Acute Lower Respiratory Infections in Children: An Observational StudyPrashant Kumar¹, Brajesh Kumar², Gopal Shankar Sahni³¹Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India³Associate and HOD, Department of Pediatrics, SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India

Received: 11-07-2023 Revised: 14-08-2023 / Accepted: 27-09-2023

Corresponding author: Dr. Brajesh Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Aim:** The aim of this study was to study clinical predictors of hypoxemia in patients of acute lower respiratory infections in children**Material & Methods:** The observational prospective study was conducted in the Pediatric Ward and Pediatric Intensive Care Unit. This was a hospital-based study completed for 1 year. The sample size taken for this study was 200. All children admitted with acute lower respiratory tract infections between the age group of 2 months to 5 years of age and diagnosed with pneumonia or bronchiolitis were included in the study.**Results:** A total of 200 cases were enrolled in the study, out of which 144 were male and 56 were female. Out of the 200 cases enrolled, 98 were below the age of 12 months and 102 were above 12 months of age. The mean age was 15.5 months. The most common and significant symptoms were rapid breathing and difficulty breathing. The least common symptom was noisy breathing and pain in the abdomen. 72 cases out of the total 200 were diagnosed to have bronchiolitis, whereas 128 cases had pneumonia. Tachypnea (87%), pallor (85%) and nasal flaring (82%), crepitations (added sounds), and subcostal retractions had better sensitivity for detecting hypoxemia. However, these signs had low specificity for hypoxemia. Head nodding (94%), intercostal retractions (84%), and cyanosis (87%) were highly specific for predicting hypoxemia. Males 138 out of 144 were significantly more hypoxemic than females 52 out of 56. Most cases have moderate hypoxemia which includes 80%.**Conclusion:** It was observed that a combination of clinical signs and symptoms can be used to predict hypoxemia when facilities of pulse oximetry and arterial blood gas analysis are not available, especially in low-resource settings.**Keywords:** Bronchiolitis, Clinical predictors, Hypoxemia, Pneumonia.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Hypoxaemia is the most serious manifestation of severe pneumonia in children. The case fatality rate of pneumonia is inversely related to the arterial haemoglobin oxygen saturation (SaO₂). [1] As respiratory infections are one of the main causes of death in children in developing countries, [2 3] and the delivery of oxygen to hypoxaemic children may improve the outcome, the detection of hypoxaemia is important. The most reliable way to do this is an arterial blood gas analysis or the determination of the arterial haemoglobin SaO₂ by pulse oximeter. However, machines to make these measurements are expensive, need constant maintenance, and are not widely available in developing countries.

Acute Respiratory infection accounts for 4 million death that occur in children under 5 years of age each year, two thirds of these deaths are in infants.

Almost all ARI deaths in young children are due to acute lower respiratory infection, mostly pneumonia. [4] One systematic review of the published literature of cohort studies reporting the frequency of hypoxaemia in children under 5 years of age with acute lower respiratory infection and the association between hypoxaemia and the risk of dying observed the prevalence of hypoxaemia 47.0% among hospitalized cases of ARI and 72.0% cases in those with radio graphically confirmed pneumonia in 23 health centers from 10 countries. [5] There are many studies which showed the prevalence of hypoxaemia in ALRI varying between 4%-83% of the cases. [6,7] A recent review of predictors of hypoxaemia also identified grunting and nasal flaring along with above mentioned signs. [5] Pulse oximeters, although relatively expensive are very useful in the detection

of early hypoxaemia and require little maintenance. [8] However, detection of hypoxemia by use of oximetry is not feasible in most situations in developing countries. Therefore, it is important to accurately identify hypoxaemic children by use of clinical signs alone.

Therefore, to help health-care professionals decide that children are hypoxemic and might benefit from oxygen it is important to accurately identify by the abuse of clinical signs alone. The diagnosis is clinical and is made on the basis of symptoms and signs such as fever, cough, rapid breathing, grunting, wheeze, crepitations without performing any investigations, and due to the unavailability of pulse oximetry at peripheral level, it is important to study which clinical predictors of hypoxemia we can reliably sort out for initiation of oxygen therapy. The duration and severity of hypoxemia is important and its early recognition and appropriate treatment improve the outcome of these children.

The aim of this study was to study clinical predictors of hypoxemia in patients of acute lower respiratory infections in children

Materials & Methods

The observational prospective study was conducted in the Pediatric Ward and Pediatric Intensive Care Unit of SKMCH, Muzaffarpur, Bihar, India. This was a hospital-based study completed for 1 year. The sample size taken for this study was 200. All children admitted with acute lower respiratory tract infections between the age group of 2 month to 5 years of age and diagnosed with pneumonia or bronchiolitis were included in the study. Any child suffering from chronic respiratory illness, congenital heart disease, severe dehydration, severe anemia, and congestive cardiac failure or shock was excluded from the study. The case children had an arterial haemoglobin SaO₂ of < 90%, measured by pulse oximeter. This SaO₂ is generally considered to reflect severe hypoxaemia.

Diagnosis of acute lower respiratory tract infection is purely clinical on the basis of the presence of symptoms such as fever, cough, rapid breathing, noisy breathing, difficulty in breathing, refusal to feed, and convulsions and signs such as tachypnea, cyanosis, wheezing, grunting, use of accessory muscles of respiration, and presence of added sounds on auscultation or abnormal sounds. [9]

Hypoxemia has been defined as per Pediatric Advanced Life Support guidelines as SpO₂ less than 94% and classified as ¹⁰

- Mild – 94–90%
- Moderate – 85–90%
- Severe – <85%

After due approval from the Ethical Committee, any child presenting with difficulty in breathing and coughing as per the ARI control program and diagnosed with Pneumonia or bronchiolitis and after obtaining consent from parents were included in the study. He/she was subjected to detailed history and clinical examination for the presence of the above signs and symptoms. Arterial saturation of all patients was recorded using a portable pulse oximeter and ABG was done. The degree of hypoxemia between ABG and SpO₂ was correlated. After obtaining a detailed history, and examination, vital parameters were recorded such as the general condition of the child/infant, heart rate, respiratory rate, saturation (SpO₂), temperature, level of consciousness, pallor, cyanosis, and head nodding and other significant clinical findings such as tachypnea, retractions, adventitious sounds such as crepitations, wheeze, and rhonchi were also taken into account. Tachypnea which is considered to be a compensatory mechanism to maintain minute ventilation [11] was defined as per the WHO age-specific cutoff values. [10] ABG was recorded in all patients as it is the gold standard to diagnose hypoxemia to correlate the degree of hypoxemia as per the ABG with the clinical predictors mentioned above.

Statistical Analysis

Analyses were performed using SPSS for Windows, SAS for Windows, and Epi-Info software packages. Analysis of the result was done in the form of sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value. p-value of <0.05% was considered to be statistically significant and the Chi-square test, t-test, and ANOVA will be used whenever required for data analysis.

Results

Table 1: Demographic details

Gender	N%
Male	144 (72)
Female	56 (28)
Age groups	
Below 12 months	98 (49)
Above 12 months	102 (51)
Symptoms	
Rapid breathing	72 (36)

Difficulty breathing	64 (32)
Fever	16 (8)
Nasal discharge	14 (7)
Cough	12 (6)
Noisy breathing	12 (6)
Pain abdomen	10 (5)
Diagnosis	
Bronchiolitis	72 (36)
Pneumonia	128 (64)

A total of 200 cases were enrolled in the study, out of which 144 were male and 56 were female. Out of the 200 cases enrolled, 98 were below the age of 12 months and 102 were above 12 months of age. The mean age was 15.5 months. The most common

and significant symptoms were rapid breathing and difficulty breathing. The least common symptom was noisy breathing and pain in the abdomen. 72 cases out of the total 200 were diagnosed to have bronchiolitis, whereas 128 cases had pneumonia.

Table 2: Sensitivity and specificity of hypoxemic signs

Signs	Sensitivity	Specificity
Pallor	85	35
Cyanosis	42	87
Level of consciousness	34	75
Tachypnea	87	29
Nasal flaring	82	42
Supraclavicular	75	35
Intercostal	56	84
Subcostal	72	22
Wheeze	26	92
Crepitations	82	18
Head nodding	14	94

Tachypnea (87%), pallor (85%) and nasal flaring (82%), crepitations (added sounds), and subcostal retractions had better sensitivity for detecting hypoxemia. However, these signs had low specificity for hypoxemia. Head nodding (94%), intercostal retractions (84%), and cyanosis (87%) were highly specific for predicting hypoxemia.

Table 3: Staging of hypoxemia and its gender-wise distribution

Hypoxemia	Male (%)	Female (%)	p-value
Mild (80)	56	24	.0007
Moderate (80)	65	15	
Severe (30)	17	13	
No (10)	6	4	
Total	144	56	

Males 138 out of 144 were significantly more hypoxemic than females 52 out of 56. Most cases have moderate hypoxemia which includes 80%.

Discussion

Globally, pneumonia is a leading cause of death among children <5 years old, accounting for >90% of acute lower respiratory infection-related deaths. [12] Hypoxaemia is a major complication of pneumonia, associated with an increase in the risk of death with increasing severity of hypoxaemia. [13] Definitions of hypoxaemia have not been uniform (being often based on the practicality of limited oxygen supplies). [14] Investigators have defined hypoxaemia from <96.6% to <90% oxygen saturation at sea level and <85% to <88% at higher altitudes. [15] For simplicity, a couple of on-going

international multicenter clinical trials for pneumonia therapy are using cut-offs of <90% at sea level and <88% at higher altitude to define hypoxaemia. [16] WHO defined hypoxemia as an SaO2 < 90% by pulse oximetry. Hypoxaemia is a common and serious complication in severely ill children.17 Most severely ill children with hypoxaemia present with clinical signs of pneumonia. [17,18] Hypoxaemia is one of the major risks of death from pneumonia, and much work has been carried out looking at clinical signs of hypoxemia in patients with pneumonia. [19,20]

A total of 200 cases were enrolled in the study, out of which 144 were male and 56 were female. Out of the 200 cases enrolled, 98 were below the age of 12 months and 102 were above 12 months of age. The mean age was 15.5 months. The most common

and significant symptoms were rapid breathing and difficulty breathing. The least common symptom was noisy breathing and pain in the abdomen. 72 cases out of the total 200 were diagnosed to have bronchiolitis, whereas 128 cases had pneumonia. In contrast, Motwani et al. [21], in their study of 204 cases, observed hypoxemia to be more common in females as compared to males. Basnet et al. [22], in their study on 150 children under 5 years, assessed the accuracy of clinical signs to differentiate lower and upper respiratory tract infections and observed that rapid breathing and fast breathing were significantly associated with hypoxemia. Redd et al. [23] in their study on 950 children ascertained that the most common symptoms were cough (99%) and difficulty in breathing (17%), running nose was observed to be the next most common symptom in their study which was not similar to our study as the most common symptom was rapid and difficulty in breathing.

Tachypnea (87%), pallor (85%) and nasal flaring (82%), crepitations (added sounds), and subcostal retractions had better sensitivity for detecting hypoxemia. However, these signs had low specificity for hypoxemia. Head nodding (94%), intercostal retractions (84%), and cyanosis (87%) were highly specific for predicting hypoxemia. Children with pneumonia often presented with hypoxaemia and remained hypoxaemic for longer compared to those without pneumonia. Children with pneumonia present with inflammation in the lung parenchyma and often experience increased oxygen demand and inadequate oxygen supply due to the reduction of diffusion of oxygen at the level of the blood gas barrier at alveolar region of respiratory zone of lung leading to hypoxaemia. A number of physical signs were highly significantly associated with hypoxaemia, but the sensitivity of each sign alone was low. Cyanosis has long been known to be associated with hypoxaemia, [24,25] but the difficulty of its detection, especially in children with dark pigmentation of the skin, makes it an insensitive marker. In our study, the respiratory rate was a poor predictor of hypoxaemia, as found in other studies. [26,27] Males 138 out of 144 were significantly more hypoxemic than females 52 out of 56. Most cases have moderate hypoxemia which includes 80%.

Conclusion

It was observed that a combination of clinical signs and symptoms can be used to predict hypoxemia when facilities of pulse oximetry and arterial blood gas analysis are not available, especially in low-resource settings. Tachypnea, pallor and nasal flaring, crepitations, and subcostal retractions are highly sensitive, whereas head nodding, intercostal retractions, and cyanosis were highly specific clinical signs for predicting hypoxemia. However, ABG analysis remains the gold standard to predict

hypoxemia. Early detection can lead to prompt intervention by instituting oxygen therapy, thus reducing mortality and morbidity due to acute lower respiratory tract infections.

References

1. Onyango FE, Steinhoff MC, Wafula EM, Wariua S, Musia J, Kitonyi J. Hypoxaemia in young Kenyan children with acute lower respiratory infection. *British Medical Journal*. 1993 Mar 6;306(6878):612-5.
2. Garenne M, Ronsmans C, Campbell H. The magnitude of mortality from acute respiratory infections in children under 5 years in developing countries. *World health statistics quarterly*. 1992 Jan 1; 45:180-.
3. Reich MR. World bank, world development report 1993: investing in health. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*. 1997;45: 899-903.
4. World Health Organization. Acute respiratory infections in children: case management in small hospitals in developing countries, a manual for doctors and other senior health workers. World Health Organization; 1990.
5. Lozano J. Epidemiology of hypoxaemia in children with acute lower respiratory infection [oxygen therapy in children]. *The international journal of tuberculosis and lung disease*. 2001 Jun 1;5(6):496-504.
6. Weber MW, Usen S, Palmer A, Jaffar S, Mulholland EK. Predictors of hypoxaemia in hospital admissions with acute lower respiratory tract infection in a developing country. *Archives of disease in childhood*. 1997 Apr 1;76(4):310-4.
7. Usen S, Weber M, Mulholland K, Jaffar S, Oparaugo A, Omosigho C, Adegbola R, Greenwood B. Clinical predictors of hypoxaemia in Gambian children with acute lower respiratory tract infection: prospective cohort study. *Bmj*. 1999 Jan 9;318(7176):86-91.
8. Qazi, S. (2002). Oxygen therapy for Acute Respiratory Infection in young children. *Indian Pediatrics*, 39, 909-913.
9. Li MY, Kelly J, Subhi R, Were W, Duke T. Global use of the WHO pocket book of hospital care for children. *Paediatrics and international child health*. 2013 Feb 1;33(1):4-11.
10. Arora M, Rai PL, Prasad PL. Clinical predictors of hypoxemia in patients of acute lower respiratory tract infections: A hospital-based study: Clinical predictors of hypoxemia. *Indian Journal of Child Health*. 2022 Nov 28: 200-3.
11. Eichenwald EC, Hansen AR. Cloherty and Stark's Manual of Neonatal Care, South Asian

- Edition. Gurgaon, Haryana: Wolters Kluwer India Pvt. Ltd. 2021.
12. Rudan I, Boschi-Pinto C, Biloglav Z, Mulholland K, Campbell H. Epidemiology and etiology of childhood pneumonia. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 2008; 86:408-16B.
 13. Mower, W. R., Sachs, C., Nicklin, E. L., & Baraff, L. J. Pulse oximetry as a fifth pediatric vital sign. *Pediatrics*, 1997; 99(5): 681-686.
 14. Laman, M., Ripa, P., Vince, J., & Tefuarani, N. Can clinical signs predict hypoxaemia in Papua New Guinean children with moderate and severe pneumonia? *Annals of tropical paediatrics*, 2005;25(1): 23-27.
 15. Lozano, J. Epidemiology of hypoxaemia in children with acute lower respiratory infection [oxygen therapy in children]. *The international journal of tuberculosis and lung disease*, 2001;5(6): 496-504.
 16. Qazi, S. Oxygen therapy for Acute Respiratory Infection in young children. *Indian Pediatrics*, 2002;39: 909-913.
 17. World Health Organization. Pocket book of hospital care for children: guidelines for the management of common illnesses with limited resources. World Health Organization. 2005.
 18. Weber, M. W., Usen, S., Palmer, A., Jaffar, S., & Mulholland, E. K. Predictors of hypoxaemia in hospital admissions with acute lower respiratory tract infection in a developing country. *Archives of disease in childhood*, 1997;76(4): 310-314.
 19. Lodha, R., Bhadauria, P. S., Kuttikat, A. V., Puranik, M., Gupta, S., Pandey, R. M., & Kabra, S. K. Can clinical symptoms or signs accurately predict hypoxemia in children with acute lower respiratory tract infections? *Indian pediatrics*, 2004;41(2): 129-136.
 20. Duke, T., Mgone, J., & Frank, D. Hypoxaemia in children with severe pneumonia in Papua New Guinea [oxygen therapy in children]. *The International Journal of Tuberculosis and Lung Disease*, 2001;5(6): 511-519.
 21. Motwani NP, Janakiraman L, Subramaniam S, Bhawani D. Clinical predictors of hypoxemia in children with acute lower respiratory illness. *Int Res J Med Sci*. 2015; 3:11-5.
 22. Basnet S, Adhikari RK, Gurung CK. Hypoxemia in children with pneumonia and its clinical predictors. *The Indian journal of pediatrics*. 2006 Sep; 73:777-81.
 23. Redd SC, Vreuls R, Metsing M, Mohobane PH, Patrick E, Moteetee M. Clinical signs of pneumonia in children attending a hospital outpatient department in Lesotho. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*. 1994;72 (1):113.
 24. Stadie WC. The oxygen of the arterial and venous blood in pneumonia and its relation to cyanosis. *The Journal of Experimental Medicine*. 1919 Sep 1;30(3):215-40.
 25. Simpson H, Flenley DC. Arterial blood-gas tensions and pH in acute lower-respiratory-tract infections in infancy and childhood. *The Lancet*. 1967 Jan 7;289(7480):7-12.
 26. Mulholland EK, Olinsky A, Shann FA. Clinical findings and severity of acute bronchiolitis. *The Lancet*. 1990 May 26;335 (8700):1259-61.
 27. Margolis PA, Ferkol TW, Marsocci S, Super DM, Keyes LL, McNutt R, Harrell Jr FE. Accuracy of the clinical examination in detecting hypoxemia in infants with respiratory illness. *The Journal of pediatrics*. 1994 Apr 1;124(4):552-60.